

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education
Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School
Address: Ermin Garcia St, corner EDSA,
Brgy. Pinagkaisahan, Quezon City
Tel No: (02) 637 6754

MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Different Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness

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MARK JONEL V. ABAD
JOHN VINCENT A. ANIANO
JEMALYN J. AVILA
ANDREI NATHANIEL D. BATUGAL
MARC ANDRIE M. BERMUNDO
IRA MAE M. CAMPOLLO
MARJORIE J. CORTIGUERRA
MARY JOY R. JALANDONI
Proponents

MS. GENEROSA E. IBASCO
Inquiries, Investigations, and Immersion
(3I) Teacher

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MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Different Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness

¹ABAD, Mark Jonel V., ¹ANIANO, John Vincent A., ¹AVILA, Jemalyn J., ¹BATUGAL, Andrei Nathaniel D., ¹BERMUNDO, Marc Andrie M., ¹CAMPOLLO, Ira Mae M., ¹CORTIGUERRA, Marjorie J., ¹JALANDONI, Mary Joy R., and ²IBASCO, Generosa E., Teacher I

¹Proponents, and ²Research Teacher, Ramon Magsaysay
(Cubao) High School - Senior High School Department (RMCHS - SHS)

ABSTRACT

As students desire an active role in their own care, as well-informed lifestyle choices and caution are stimulated to improve personal health, and as public health concerns require increased epidemiological surveillance, including public literacy and attention, communication of medical terms over the lay-professional boundary increases in volume and importance. Students develop general knowledge regarding the pandemic, for most students' collected most of the "Medical Terms" from Television, Newspapers, or Social Media. Besides, students are also health consumers. They need reliable medical information and get it from reliable resources. They just don't obtain it from physicians because they also obtain that type of information through searching on the web, direct-to-consumer advertising, and patient education. Celebrities and News outlets have a big responsibility on their shoulders, for their influence could affect what type of information is being spread.

Hence, cross-boundary communications, semantics and understanding of medical ideas are serious barriers. Students often do not understand technical terms and explanations or interpret them inaccurately, contingent on their personal and cultural experiences or background, education levels, and cognitive and affective states of mind. Again, medical professionals may have a hard time properly interpreting lay health expressions and associated conceptualizations, but they could provide or spread accurate information. Thus, research on students expresses medical ideas provides

insights that help bridge the semantics and terminology gap in bi-directional health-related communication between laypersons and professionals.

Although the “consumer vocabulary problem” has long been acknowledged, “personal health vocabularies have only recently been meeting the expense significance in the literature. While terminologies for medical professionals continue to evolve, few consumer-level vocabularies have been inspected As Lewis et al. viewed, “The development of a consumer vocabulary should be based on research that includes consumer information needs and consumers’ ways of talking about and expressing those needs”. This suggestion parallels the power of semantics towards students’ (as health consumers) involvement in their pandemic awareness.

Keywords: *semantics, terminologies, COVID-19, vocabulary, awareness*

CHAPTER 1:

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare consumers, especially those who are still studying, often have difficulty expressing and comprehending medical concepts. In particular, concepts related to the field of medicine in the viewpoint of students were characterized confirming the degree to which they mapped to professional medical vocabularies. In addition, this is a widely known language gap between students and health care professionals. This gap may hinder effective communication between the two groups thus affecting consumers' health information seeking and ensuing decision making regarding their health issues and their pandemic awareness.

Alongside with this, online patient portals, health websites, and health articles have been widely adopted in the Philippines in a nationwide effort to promote and raise awareness regarding the pandemic, and we found out that when searching online health information, using only consumer terms leads to poor information retrieval results. Even though the Department of Health has an official website, the website itself does not address misconceptions, especially regarding common medical health terms. Nonetheless, medical terms remain a major obstacle for public health consumers especially students to comprehend medical terms. Misinterpretation of the content may result in unintended misinformation and / or misunderstanding.

This leads to the current paper's objective, which is to identify and recognize medical expressions and associated concepts used by local and international mediators as a method of action in spreading information campaigns to minimize the damages done by the COVID-19 pandemic and their relation to the effect on students' pandemic awareness.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

For this study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness*** the main question is:

MAIN QUESTION: *Does the usage of numerous terminologies in defining the imposed health protocols have an impact on the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School?*

This main question has a set of related questions to support this matter, which are the following:

SUPPORTING QUESTION #1: *What are the perspectives of the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School to the terminologies given by the World Health Organization (WHO) before and during the lockdown implemented worldwide that is caused by COVID-19?*

SUPPORTING QUESTION #2: *Does the usage of terminologies given worldwide by the World Health Organization (WHO) satisfy the need for knowledge about the pandemic to high school students?*

SUPPORTING QUESTION #3: *What are the perspectives of the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School to the terminologies given by Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) and the Department of Health (DOH) before the lockdown in the Philippines caused by COVID-19?*

SUPPORTING QUESTION #4: *What are the perspectives of the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School to the terminologies given by Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) and the Department of Health (DOH) during the lockdown in the Philippines caused by COVID-19?*

SUPPORTING QUESTION #5: *Does the usage of terminologies given worldwide by the Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) and the Department of Health (DOH) satisfy the need for knowledge about the pandemic to high school students?*

SUPPORTING QUESTION #6: *What could be recommended to the parties involved (the World Health Organization (WHO), the Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) and the Department of Health (DOH)) in order for these terminologies to be effectively distributed to high school students and by extension, people of all ages?*

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The research objectives for the study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness*** are the following:

- ❖ This study delivers a discussion of having knowledge on terminologies in a time where lockdowns are prevalent and dissemination of accurate information is crucial.
- ❖ This study reflects the substantial effects of the usage of numerous health protocol terminologies on the students' level of pandemic awareness to the government as well as the scientific community.
- ❖ This study is essential for the benefit not only to the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, but also to the general public, as it is oriented on semantics and the usage of different terminologies in a time of community quarantine prevalence.

THESIS STATEMENT

With the pandemic situation in the Philippines is becoming a major problem in line with various other factors, students especially those in the in the secondary levels would be less inclined to be attentive in assessing the situation regarding the information released about the pandemic and its effects, due to the effects of the new normal set-up in learning inside the household. This in turn, would make these high school students rather come in their classes during their online and home-based sessions and subsequently after the sessions have been ended, do labor into their household chores or tend to rest to relieve themselves of the undesirable facets of the new set-up.

Due to the fact that the system of K-12 essentially makes it easier for students to work after graduation, as well as provide skills in their corresponding tracks, it is not inevitable that many of them, particularly those in the lower income bracket, will work for their families or stop for a while before taking into college In order to recover from the heavy toll of the pandemic into their lives, while some of the students may face this dilemma much earlier, as they live in rural areas or a part of the urban poor that both has the disadvantages to go further in this online classroom set-up. While this may be too far-fetched upon the scope of our topic, it is an imperative thing to note into while taking this topic into account.

As the new education system that was being followed by the Department of Education was enacted in a blaze, most of the schools wherein the curriculum was just introduced to the spur-of-the-moment lengthened stay of students, the influx of students as well as the lack of materials, classrooms and teachers qualified to teach. Thus, the implementation of the curriculum was ill prepared and was not planned for properly, leading to students perceiving their schools as inadequate in some areas. This has been worsened by the time of the COVID-19 pandemic, as not all schools are totally prepared by the downgrades brought by the new education system. While students may not totally give it out or say it, it is impossible to have a student that will be satisfied with the education system that is with today, and it degrades their learning capabilities.

With the terminologies given by numerous parties involved in taking down the disease's threat as early as possible along with the mix of the media and political factors in the Philippines, an array of misinformation and unusualness may be contemporary on

the students as they continue to accomplish in their online classes as well as being bombarded by the effects of the pandemic every day until a day comes that the menace is mitigated.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

With the root cause of the current pandemic is the unnatural spread of a new disease unknown to humanity, it has not only wreaked havoc by affecting the physical health of people worldwide, but also raised the foundations of another swarm of misunderstanding of the civilians to different technical and legal terms that have been utilized in official governmental guidance, media reports, and throughout the general public with respect to the 2019-nCoV and the resulting COVID-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019).

The National Cancer Institute or NCI, defines in their dictionary that the term health protocol as a detailed plan of a scientific or medical experiment, treatment, or procedure. In clinical trials, it states what the study will do, how it will be done, and why it is being done. It explains how many people will be in the study, who is eligible to take part in it, what study drugs or other interventions will be given, what tests will be done and how often, and what information will be collected.

Ensuring that the accurate information is the key to understand how and why it's important to prevent the spread of COVID-19. But that can be difficult when faced with the increasing amount of complicated terminology that has developed, seemingly overnight, around the coronavirus outbreak. In a statement by Meyer (2020) "If you want to be able to respond to things in a clear way, you must have a clear understanding of what we're talking about".

While there are many theories regarding on how to deal with the effects of the virus in a scientific manner, the purpose of this paper is aiming towards the knowledge of the terminologies released by both international and local sources and therefore, the theory of health literacy is more relevant to the current study. By definition, health literacy is

linked to literacy and entails people's knowledge, motivation, and competence to access, understand, appraise and apply health information in order to make judgments and take decisions in everyday life concerning healthcare, disease prevention, and health promotion to maintain or improve quality of life during the life course (Sørensen et al., 2012, p. 3).

The framework also reflects how factors external to the individual (e.g., family, setting, community, culture, and media) influence the constructs and relations represented in the framework. The framework is organized into 4 primary components: (a) factors that influence the development and use of health literacy skills; (b) health-related stimuli; (c) health literacy skills needed to comprehend the stimulus and perform the task; and (d) mediators between health literacy and health outcomes.

In another definition, the theory of health literacy is a concept that summarizes the fact that individuals must be "literate" in terms of skills that "maintain or improve health" (Hepburn, 2012, p. 230). Hepburn in 2012 provides a comprehensive amount of the skills included in the theory, which are cognitive (knowledge), behavioral (functional), advocacy (proactive) and existential (spiritual). This also involves the incorporation of basic skills such as reading, writing and numeracy, and foster the ability to effectively analyze, communicate and question existing information in order to make sense of life with uncertainty and illness" (p. 230).

Adding to this, according to Hepburn (2012), here are three levels of health literacy: level I or functional literacy, which is the "ability to apply basic health literacy skills, such as reading and understanding medication labels"; level II or interactive health literacy, which "involves use of cognitive skills and operate in a social environment supports social participation in health-related issues in the community"; and level III or critical literacy, which "incorporates the ability to evaluate health issues, determine the challenges and advantages of specific issues, recognize the potential benefit of a particular strategy, and offer advice at the community level".

Health literacy necessitates that an individual has or develop the competence to understand health information and be proactive relative to health-related. Hepburn (2012)

goes on to state that it is in regard to health literacy where clinicians may fail – a clinician may not have the right or adequate expertise to address all levels.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

For this paper’s conceptual framework, the visualization that is shown below shows the contributory factors, effects, and outcomes of the aforementioned factors to figure out what are the effects of having to partake and list down the said issues at hand. As seen in the graph, the main topic, which is centered in the visualization, shows a significant connection to the terminologies that are being used locally and internationally, the effects of the said terms, which are the introduction of new terms, the confusion that is being brought up to it, and being uncertain or being naïve towards the meaning of the said terminologies, which boils down to the connection made to the center of this topic towards

the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, which where will the population and the sampling of the paper will be conducted.

The researchers speculate that the usage of numerous vocabularies since the implementation of the healthcare protocols to minimize the spread of the illness has a noteworthy scientific relationship to the pandemic awareness of the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School, they will be affected by the effects that the terminologies introduced before the start of pandemic happened and has the probability to be unaware of other terminologies for other jargon related to the COVID-19 pandemic. But since the population that was picked on were students that are studying on Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School that are in the modality of distance learning as with compliance to the orders of the government to minimize the damages and infection rates of the pandemic, the researchers are confident that majority of the students are familiar with the terminologies that are given locally and internationally given over a year.

DEFINITION OF TERMINOLOGIES

- **Aerosol / Droplet Nuclei** (*noun*) - A substance enclosed under pressure and able to be released as a fine spray, typically by means of a propellant gas.
- **Antibody** (*noun*) - A protein found on the blood that is produced in response to and counteracting a specific antigen. Antibodies combine chemically with substances which the body recognizes as alien, such as bacteria, viruses, and foreign substances in the blood.
- **Antibody Test / Serology Test** (*noun*) - A type of diagnostic test to check if antibodies in the blood that show that a specific pathogen being defended by the body's antibodies.
- **Antigen** (*noun*) - A toxin or other foreign substance which induces an immune response in the body, especially the production of antibodies.
- **Antigen Test / Rapid Test** (*noun*) - A type of diagnostic test that checks the antigens to see if a person is currently infected.

- **APOR** (*noun*) - An acronym for Authorized Person Outside Residence, a person with the authority to buy out and go outside for certain conditions during the state of ECQ in the Philippines.
- **Asymptomatic** (*adjective*) - A condition where a person shows no signs of symptoms.
- **Carrier** (*noun*) - A person or animal that transmits a disease-causing organism to others. Typically, the carrier suffers no symptoms of the disease.
- **Clinical Trial / Trial** (*noun*) - A situation where researchers study a medical test or treatment in a set group of people to make sure it's safe and effective before giving it to the public.
- **Close Contact** (*noun*) - A contact from one person to another within a distance of one meter.
- **Cluster** (*noun*) - A grouping of disease cases in a geographic area during a set time period.
- **Community Quarantine** (*noun*) - The practice of a community to minimize a spread of a disease by staying at home and away from others for two weeks to check if an infection has been present in the area.
- **Conjunctiva** (*noun*) - The mucous membrane that covers the front of the eye and lines the inside of the eyelids.
- **Contact Tracing** (*noun*) - A type of disease control measure where public health workers known as contact tracers work with infected people to identify who had close contact with them while they were contagious.
- **Convalescent Plasma Therapy** (*noun*) - A treatment that involves taking blood from someone who has antibodies to a disease, separating out the clear liquid part (plasma), and then giving it to someone who is sick with the same illness.
- **Coronavirus** (*noun*) - A type of virus that looks like a corona (crown) when viewed under a microscope.
- **COVID-19** (*noun*) - Acronym for coronavirus disease-19.
- **Diagnostic Test** (*noun*) - A preliminary test that checks if a person has been infected.

- **Drive-Thru Testing** (*noun*) – A test that instead of visiting a doctor's office or other indoor facility for health care, patients pull up in their cars to a specific outdoor site where tests are being done.
- **Droplet** (*noun*) - A tiny moist particle that is released by a person when excreting bodily fluids.
- **Droplet Transmission** (*noun*) - Occurs when a person is in close contact with someone who has symptoms of a certain disease.
- **Emergency Use Authorization** (*noun*) - A ruling put out by the higher authorities in case of an emergency, allowing medical professionals to use certain products before they even have the agency's full approval, clearance, or licensing.
- **Endemic** (*adjective*) - A situation of a disease or condition that is regularly found among particular people or in a certain area.
- **Enhanced Community Quarantine** (*noun*) - Also known as ECQ, is a state of community quarantine in the Philippines with the highest number of restrictions.
- **Epidemic** (*noun*) - A widespread occurrence of an infectious disease in a community at a particular time.
- **Flattening the Curve** (*noun*) - Refers to efforts designed to prevent too many people from getting sick around the same time, which would overwhelm the system of health care in a country.
- **General Community Quarantine** (*noun*) - Also known as GCQ, is a state of community quarantine in the Philippines with minimized number of restrictions compared to ECQ.
- **IATF-EID** (*noun*) - Acronym for Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Diseases
- **Incubation Period** (*noun*) – Refers to the time period where an infectious disease enters the body until early symptoms show up.
- **Infect** (*verb*) - To affect a person or another organism with a disease-causing organism.
- **Infusion** (*noun*) - A procedure that puts a medicine, blood, or fluid directly into the veins through an IV or catheter over a period of time.

- **Herd Immunity** (*noun*) - A scenario where the majority of people in an area are immune to a specific infection, even the members of the population (herd) are protected simply by being around them. Anywhere from 50% to 90% of the population would have to have antibodies to a certain disease in order for herd immunity to kick in.
- **High-Risk** (*adjective*) - Involving or exposed to a high level of danger.
- **Local Transmission** (*noun*) - The transfer of an infectious disease that causes the disease in a local geographical setting.
- **Lockdown** (*noun*) - A state of isolation or restricted access instituted as a security measure.
- **Mandatory** (*adjective*) - Required by law or regulations; compulsory.
- **Mandatory Quarantine** (*noun*) - An order from a higher authority telling the people in a certain area to undergo quarantine to avoid spreading an infectious disease.
- **Mass Testing** (*noun*) - A term that refers to a widespread acquisition of people to be tested to a certain infectious disease.
- **Mild** (*adjective*) - A rule or a punishment with of only moderate severity or of an illness or pain being not serious or dangerous.
- **Modified** (*verb*) - To make partial or minor changes to (something), typically so as to improve it or to make it less extreme.
- **Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine** (*noun*) - Also known as MECQ, this is a modified version of ECQ, a state of community quarantine in the Philippines with the highest number of restrictions.
- **Modified General Community Quarantine** (*noun*) - Also known as MGCQ, this is a modified version of GCQ, a state of community quarantine in the Philippines with minimized number of restrictions compared to ECQ.
- **Mortality Rate** (*noun*) - The measure of the number of deaths (in general, or due to a specific cause) in a particular population, scaled to the size of that population, per unit of time.
- **N95 Mask / N95 Respirator** (*noun*) - A mask designed to prevent the wearer from breathing in tiny particles. When fit properly, they filter out at least 95% of large and small particles.

- **New Normal** (*noun*) - A situation where people are forced to live in a world facing a global crisis, such as a pandemic.
- **Outbreak** (*noun*) - The sudden or violent start of something unwelcome, such as a disease.
- **Pandemic** (*noun*) - An epidemic that has spread to several countries or continents.
- **Patient Zero** (*noun*) - Refers to a person spotted with the first case of an infectious disease in an area.
- **PCR Test** (*noun*) - An acronym for polymerase chain reaction test, a diagnostic test that determines if a person is infected by analyzing a sample to see if it contains genetic material from a virus.
- **Personal Protective Equipment** (*noun*) - Also known as PPE, are special clothes and accessories designed to protect health care workers from infectious diseases like COVID-19 while in close contact with patients and other people.
- **Physical Distancing** (*noun*) - A practice under social distancing where people are avoiding close contact to other persons.
- **Pre-symptomatic** (*noun*) - A situation where a person has contracted the virus and may soon feel symptoms, but doesn't have any at the moment.
- **Quarantine** (*noun*) - The practice of staying home and away from others for two weeks after being exposed to an infectious disease.
- **R₀** (*noun*) - Pronounced as r-naught, this refers to the "basic reproductive number" of a contagious disease: the average number of additional cases that directly result from a single person bringing it into a community.
- **Respiratory Illness** (*noun*) - A type of disease that affects the lungs and other parts of the respiratory system.
- **SARS-CoV-2** (*noun*) - Stands for severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2. SARS-CoV-2 is the specific strain of coronavirus that causes the COVID-19 disease.
- **Self-Isolation** (*noun*) - Refers to staying in a contained area to avoid infecting others.
- **Serology Test** (*noun*) - See Antibody Test.

- **Social Distancing** (*noun*) - The practice of keeping extra space between two people with six feet being the minimum recommended amount to prevent spreading diseases. Canceling large gatherings, working at home instead of an office, and switching from in-person school to remote learning are parts of social distancing.
- **State of Emergency** (*noun*) - A declaration made by the one of the higher authorities in a state or an area because a disaster is occurring or about to occur.
- **Swab Test / Viral Test** (*noun*) - A type of diagnostic test that involves taking sample from the back of the nasal cavity so it can be analyzed in a lab to see if it contains a pathogen.
- **Triage** (*noun*) - The assignment of degrees of urgency to wounds or illnesses to decide the order of treatment of a large number of patients or casualties.
- **Trial** (*noun*) - See Clinical Trial.
- **Vaccine** (*noun*) - A kind of medicine that prevents disease by training your body's immune system to fight a germ or a virus that it's never come into contact with before.
- **Variant** (*noun*) - A change or alteration in relation to its originated source.
- **Ventilator** (*noun*) - A machine used to pump air into your lungs if they aren't working properly on their own.
- **Viral Dose / Viral Load** (*noun*) - Refers to the amount of virus a person is exposed to.
- **Viral Load** (*noun*) - See Viral Dose.
- **Viral Shedding** (*noun*) - The release of virus from an infected person into the environment, where it can infect others.
- **Viral Test** (*noun*) - See Swab Test.
- **Virus** (*noun*) - A tiny infectious organism made up of genetic material (DNA or RNA) wrapped in a protein coat. Viruses can't multiply on their own; they reproduce by invading living cells and taking control of them.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The design's approach of the study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness*** is quantitative; since it focuses more on the ability to complete statistical analysis (Mersdorf, 2016).

A survey research design was employed in this study to establish a foundation in finding out the effects of using various terms for the health protocols to their cognizance to the events during the pandemic caused by COVID-19.

To give light to its definition, survey research design is an extensive cross-sectional approach, where a number of cases are considered at a particular time and the data is gathered to study the opinions, behavior, attitudes, habits, desires, values and beliefs etc. (Farooq, 2015).

DATA MATRIX

<i>Data Needed</i>	<i>Available Sources</i>	<i>Method of Analysis</i>	<i>Ethical Aspects Involved</i>
1. Overview of COVID-19 Origins	Secondary Materials (Books, Journals, Government Statistics, News Reports, etc.)	Literature Review Analysis of Themes and Subthemes Related to Broader Concepts and Theory	Acknowledge and Properly Cite all Secondary Sources
2. Insights of the Effects of COVID-19	Secondary Materials (Books, Journals, Government Statistics, News Reports, etc.)	Literature Review Analysis of Themes and Subthemes Related to Broader Concepts and Theory	Acknowledge and Properly Cite all Secondary Sources

3. History of COVID-19 in the Philippines	Secondary Materials (Books, Journals, Government Statistics, News Reports, etc.)	Literature Review Analysis of Themes and Subthemes Related to Broader Concepts and Theory	Acknowledge and Properly Cite all Secondary Sources
4. COVID-19 Terminologies in the Philippines	Secondary Materials (Books, Journals, Government Statistics, News Reports, etc.)	Literature Review Analysis of Themes and Subthemes Related to Broader Concepts and Theory	Acknowledge and Properly Cite all Secondary Sources
5. Situation of the Philippines during Lockdown	Secondary Materials (Books, Journals, Government Statistics, News Reports, etc.)	Literature Review Analysis of Themes and Subthemes Related to Broader Concepts and Theory	Acknowledge and Properly Cite all Secondary Sources
6. Related Studies about Semantics	Secondary Materials (Books, Journals, Government Statistics, News Reports, etc.)	Literature Review Analysis of Themes and Subthemes Related to Broader Concepts and Theory	Acknowledge and Properly Cite all Secondary Sources

<p>7. Perspectives of High Schools Students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School in Regards to the Usage of Numerous Vocabularies to Disseminate Information during the Pandemic</p>	<p>Survey according to the Population of the Students in Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School</p>	<p>Quantitative Analysis</p>	<p>Acknowledgement and Verification of Consent by Provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to Survey Respondents</p>
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For the data matrix of the study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness***, there will be seven types of data that will be collected the first six types of data that will be gathered are the overview of the origins of COVID-19 in the Philippines, the insights of the effects of COVID-19, the history of COVID-19 in the context of the Philippines, the terminologies of COVID-19 in the Philippines, the situation of the Philippines during the lockdown, and the related studies about semantics. These were taken from reference materials such as books, journals and research papers which may be sourced through internet search. Analysis will be through a literature review, and will need to be correctly cited to give proper credit to the author's content where the information was taken from.

OPERATIONALIZATION

For the operationalization of the study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness***, the survey that is hosted via Google Forms is then separated by seven parts. The first part is the introductory part that is tagged along with a disclaimer

about the privacy policy in accordance to the regulations of the Philippine law, specifically Republic Act (RA) 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

The second part is the collection of the demographic profiles of the respondents, which is meant to be sorted out after the survey hits the desired number of respondents. This part includes the name of the respondent, which can be kept optional for their privacy, their gender, the current grade level that they are in, and for the students of the senior high school department, the strand that they are in.

The third part for the survey is terminologies that are officially released by the World Health Organization (WHO) in their information campaign about the COVID-19 pandemic before and during the lockdown which are composed of 13 terminologies to be asked to the survey respondent if they are familiar to the topic, or if they are unfamiliar with it or maybe they heard it as a hunch once in a while.

The fourth and fifth part of the survey for the study is similar to the third part but the focus is stressed more on the understandings of the survey respondents on terminologies given by the authorities of the Philippines before and during the lockdown to handle the dissemination of knowledge to the Filipino people. The fourth part, which focuses on terms used before the lockdown, is composed of 22 questions while the fifth part comprises of 12 questions.

The sixth part is the part of verification of consent and authorization that was being conducted by the researchers, and the final part is a note of thanks coming from the researchers as well as a request to watch a list of videos found on YouTube regarding the matter if they have the luxury of time, this has been done to educate them after the survey.

ETHICAL ASPECT

Consent for the survey respondents for the conduction of the study was asked through text messages via Facebook Messenger (refer to Appendices), detailing what the research was for and the need for respondents for the research. Before conducting the

survey, the students who will be the respondents for the survey were informed about their rights in the message with the link for the questionnaire. The researchers also properly briefed them regarding the insights of the study. They were also informed that the data gathered from them shall be kept only until the research is completed, and that no information can be used to identify them in the study. All data gathered were in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Participants especially those in the survey have the choice in the survey to keep their name optional to remain anonymous. The key informants on the other hand granted permission to the researcher for their name to be revealed and used as reference in the paper.

SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

This study shall focus foremost among the population of the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School located Cubao, Quezon City. A sample of 120 students, with 20 of them coming from a grade level of the school were surveyed, and for the senior high school department the 20 respondents each came from a variety of tracks and strands. This sampling is done due to the fact that not all students were having free time on their own since it was already the end of the school year and thus there were more activities to comply and to attend.

Additionally, the researchers also had to contend with time limitations since the students in Grade 12 were already graduating, and thus had only little window time to survey within the period of research writing. The researchers compensated for these limitations by diligently covering the lack of responses by diligently asking the students to answer the survey. As said above, a total of 120 students were surveyed.

By the creation of this research, a lot of varied sources were already available of the internet pertaining the matter of this topic, so this research has the opportunity to focus only on the perspectives of the students regarding the issue of using varied jargon in response to spreading information to combat the spread of the COVID-19 pandemic.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The significance of the study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness*** is that it elevates questions about the nature of consumer health vocabularies that we believe have theoretical and practical implications for closing the distance on the medical vocabulary gap between students (as healthcare consumers) and professionals which has a big impact on student's pandemic awareness.

CHAPTER 2:

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

Overview of COVID-19 Origins

The China Health Authority alerted the World Health Organization (WHO) on December 31, 2019 to several cases of pneumonia of unknown etiology in Wuhan City in Hubei Province in central China. Cases of this situation had been reported since December 8, 2019, and many patients of the same case have worked at or lived around the local Huanan Seafood Wholesale Market although other early cases had no exposure to this market (Lu *et. al.*, 2020).

A review by Shereen *et. al.*'s states that the COVID-19 is a highly transmittable and pathogenic viral infection caused by severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), which emerged in Wuhan, China and sustained to proliferate on the various areas of the world. As the virus is similar to the family of formerly acknowledged SARS-COV pathogens, previously used animal models are utilized to study the pathogenicity of the new virus. Similar virus variants have also been assessed in hopes to find a treatment to those who were afflicted by the disease.

Clinical indicators of COVID-19 are diverse, mirroring those of pneumonia and commonly presenting with fever, cough, myalgias, fatigue, and less commonly with

diarrhea and vomiting. This increasingly develops into severe acute respiratory infection, acute respiratory distress syndrome, acute respiratory failure, hepatic injury, kidney failure and cardiovascular complications. (Naji, 2020). Harapan *et. al.*'s literature review tells that due to rapid transmission, countries of the world must increase attention into surveillance of probable people who are infected by the disease and to scale up the readiness and response operations as a measure to mitigate the spread of the virus.

Cruz and Zeichner also expressed that the knowledge on how COVID-19 works, like on younger people where there is still much more to dig upon when it comes to the impact of this virus on children as well as the impact of children on viral spread. Rothan and Byrareddy also adds up to the former by declaring that the practice of widespread procedures to diminish the transmission are compulsory to regulate the outbreak along with distinct attention to reduce transmission in vulnerable populations. The said disease too is also moderately understood due to its intricacies in inflammatory characteristics as distinguished by McElvaney *et. al.*

Local and International Effect of COVID-19

Boissay and Rungcharoenkitkul in their study assessed the macroeconomic effects of the COVID-19 pandemic where they noted that unlike the past pandemics, the world faced a synchronized lockdown to prevent the spread of the disease. Typically, this led into the world falling into an economic trauma where the unprecedented economic sudden stop would need to be looked upon in order to see what would happen to the world economy. In conclusion, the researchers in this study stated that the course of action is fixed and ready-to-go yet the damages right now are still unprecedented. Other than that, the proper decisions between the pandemic and the economy must be needed on this day and age.

In addition to this, Caggiano *et. al.* studied that the uncertainties of the current pandemic will bring a considerable amount of economic damage that is brought by the deterioration of financial conditions that is predicted to be in place for a year. However,

they concluded that these damages would be much more likely a conservative amount rather than a full-scale economic depression.

Multi-actor innovation hubs that will support, connect, and enable businesses to recover and pivot beyond the COVID-19 pandemic is the primary recommendations that are given by Rowan and Galanakis in their review paper. They conjectured that climate action, digitization, manufacturing, and sustainable food production, security, and waste mitigation as possible candidates for boosting the economy back. In their paper, they also recommend community transitioning, training, enterprise, and employment to low carbon economies as key areas to outsource manpower for the improvement of economies of nations post-pandemic.

On assessing the agricultural cooperatives in Shanghai, China, in a paper released by Gu and Wang in 2020 have found out that the vegetable market has been heavily affected especially on the sales negotiations. where it affected the gap between the field prices and the prices sold at markets, with another revelation that the income has been declining as the pandemic goes on and that by stabilizing the market means to secure the agricultural insurance and income of farmers.

Mok *et. al.* relayed that most of the students in mainland China would want to have overseas studies plans against the impending threat of the COVID-19 pandemic. In their study, 84% of them stated that they showed no interest in studying in other countries, while the one who would want to study in other countries, specifically the United States, Hong Kong, United Kingdom, Japan, and Taiwan. The effects of the pandemic in academic institutions are also detailed by teachers such as an article published by Bush and Bentley in their narratives on the pandemic and how do they innovate and cope. The same can be also said with a paper published by Uhi in 2020 which focuses on his institution's subsidiarity to students and how does the school innovate in the "online learning" mode.

In relation to this, Shin and Kang published a paper to examine the impact of expected interaction and cleanliness on perceived health risk and hotel booking intentions of hotel customers. In their study they have noted that the theoretical implication of this is identifying the decision-making process of the customers, with the practical implications

of this is to improve the methodologies of hotel services in the tourism sector. Lee and Trimi explored the fact that sustainable innovations is a must in order for the economy to thrive even in the pandemic by using the frameworks of convergence innovation as well as discussing on how it will be operative in sustainable innovations while most of the people are in their households with limited mobility.

Yet, innovations amidst the pandemic can happen, as it was detailed by one innovative article given by Din *et. al.* on the production of protective equipment for frontliners that are combatting against the COVID-19 pandemic, that was facing a decline in supplies due to the lack of availability of the said protective equipment. The authors discussed that the pandemic opened a new opportunity in the field of computer aided 3D design. They stressed out that innovation might be made easier and faster if the utilization of CAD were to be taught as part of the standard Science, Engineering, Medical and Dental curriculum. They stated that the realization of collaborative efforts of the dental and medical profession with the academic and industry sectors can still be strengthened.

In an editorial article that was written by Škorić *et. al.*, they noted about the impact of the whopping number of articles have made professionals and the general public about the importance of scientific research and its implications during the COVID-19 pandemic. It also has shown the benefits of open access knowledge to the people but they have emphasized that well designed papers and peer reviewed methodologies is a must, which is very crucial to take notes of as other journals published in the time of the pandemic is still unsatisfactory, which can prove fatal if decisions are mostly based on impulsive desires.

Background History of COVID-19 in the Philippines

In January 2020 the word is out, there is a mysterious disease similar to severe acute respiratory disease (SARS) spreading from Wuhan, China, to neighboring countries. Philippine Health Secretary Francisco Duque III ordered the bureau of quarantine to strengthen surveillance of incoming travelers from China, but authorities stopped short of banning incoming flights from China. However, on January 29, Duque

summoned to the House of Representatives and said it would be very tricky if the Philippines singles out China for a travel ban. During the same day, a man under investigation in the Philippines for the 2019 Novel Coronavirus died due to pneumonia. The day after the news is disseminated: Coronavirus reaches Philippine Shores.

On January 30, the World Health Organization declared Novel Coronavirus a public health emergency of international concern. President Duterte also imposed travel restrictions to Hubei Province and their surrounding provinces. Until March 6, the DOH confirmed 2 new cases of Filipinos. One man in San Juan City contracts the virus through the Muslim prayer hall. The next day, DOH confirmed a local transmission happening. Now the Novel Coronavirus is loose among the populace. Moreover, on March 9, President Rodrigo Roa Duterte declared a public health emergency but still rejects a Metro Manila Lockdown idea. Two days later, DOH recorded the first local death. She is the wife of the 34th case who attended a Senate hearing on March 5 prompting several senators to quarantine.

According to Robles (2020), on March 12, President Duterte announced the lockdown of the entire Metro Manila. Land, domestic air, and domestic sea travel to and from the National Capital Region will be suspended from Sunday (March 15) to April 14, while mass gatherings have also been banned, according to local media. A month-long lockdown has left NCR's streets nearly deserted. The Philippine Capital has been sealed off to fight the pandemic. Over 13 million people living in the area have been ordered to stay home. Soon the other regions followed in response to surging cases. The restrictions switched back and forth (for a year) from ECQ to MECQ (Enhanced Community Quarantine and Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine) due to a never-ending case surge, and the threat of hospitals being overwhelmed.

The threat of Covid-19 virus extends to the hospitals and businesses and targets the service and education sector. According to John Hopkins University, this month nearly 9,000 new coronavirus infections are recorded in the Philippines as of April 26. The country now has the 2nd highest caseload in Southeast Asia after Indonesia. Hospitals

across the Philippines are being stretched to their limits, and most of the businesses are now permanently closed.

During the lockdown, a lot of things happened. These transpired into many events like how hungry Filipinos share food. Because of strict lockdown in place, hundreds of community pantries have been set up. Local people can share food and essential supplies while waiting for government aid. Next, the boom in the delivery sector (e.g. Grabfood and FoodPanda) is also prominent. Most of the restaurants today operate on 50% capacity or less, so big franchises try to gain profit by dominating the delivery sector. Also, the most affected ones being the education sector. A looming learning crisis is now prominent in the Philippines after year-long school closures during the pandemic. Many students are now struggling to adapt to the new way of learning. The pandemic has shut down schools for more than a year, forcing classes to go virtual, but many kids in low-income areas of the Philippines have no way to access online classes. The educational institutions and staff worry that the students are not learning enough. Up to this date, many people are waiting for the vaccine to arrive. President Duterte announced that he won't ease the restrictions until most of the people are vaccinated (South China Morning Post, 2021).

COVID-19 Terminologies in the Philippines

The COVID-19 pandemic has given rise to a whole new array of words and phrases all over the world; while proving helpful in mass dissemination of information on the pandemic, difficulty in understanding complicated jargons and terminologies can be quite a challenge to many. In her Yale Medicine article, Katella (2020) claimed that ensuring everyone has the correct information is “key” for the mass to understand the ways and importance of contributing in stemming the spread of the virus. In the Philippines, a dedicated site was built by Google Philippines (2020) in collaboration with University of the Philippines - Diliman (UP - Diliman) Assistant Professor Eilene Antoinette Narvaez and literature teacher Hannah Marie R. Aranas, to help provide Filipinos an

online dictionary of words related to COVID-19. As defined by Google Philippines (2020), the COVID-19 terminologies in the Philippines before and during the lockdown are the following:

The vocabulary pertaining to COVID-19 in the Philippines still continues to add up as the government continues to devise various strategies to contain local infections. Wenke (2020), as quoted in an Interaksyon article by Malasig (2020), said that while the country continues to grapple with the COVID-19 pandemic, experts also continue to receive an “overwhelming amount of information” each day. With the dissemination of new pandemic-related terminologies, many Filipinos seek to learn their meaning in their local languages.

Situation of the Philippines during Lockdown

As cases of COVID-19 cases sharply increase throughout the country, preventive measures are being acquired by the government. The President issued Proclamation No. 929 on March 16, 2020, which declared a state of calamity nationwide for the duration of six months. The proclamation also immediately enforced an Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ) throughout the island of Luzon that included the National Capital Region where the greatest number of cases were located on March 16, 2020. On the same date, a memorandum spelling out the ECQ guidelines for the management of the coronavirus contagion. The memorandum gives mandatory ordinances of home quarantine, suspension of classes and mass public transport facilities, prohibited mass gatherings and travel ban. Work from home arrangement is also recommended for public officers, however, private establishments providing necessities and activities related to food and medicine were allowed to operate.

The ECQ, together with its restrictions, was initially set until midnight of April 13, but was extended until April 30 then to May 15 in some locations. The critical zone would be placed under a “total lockdown,” meaning the residents would be under strict orders to stay at home, except for emergencies, with the local government providing for their daily needs. City mayors, with the backing of the administration, also resolved to impose stricter checkpoints, curfews, and a limit to general public mobility and economic

operations. The people also fear for their health and have changed almost every person's daily routine by showing high compliance to the directives and health protocols of the Department of Health. Many individuals tend to be less physically active, spend longer screen time, have irregular sleep patterns and unhealthy diets resulting in weight gain and loss of physical fitness (UNDESA, 2020). This indicates that almost all people recognized and were distressed about the seriousness of the situation, and the slight effectiveness of the government's efforts in instilling compliance to these practices.

However, other places are allowed to implement other community quarantines like Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine (MECQ), General Community Quarantine (GCQ), and Modified General Community Quarantine (MGCQ) depending on their level of risk. This is due to the inability of the government to uphold all current necessities so lockdowns are just implemented in places with high certain level risk of infection, this is also to slowly regain economic growth in the Philippines.

Related Studies about Semantics

One study to analyze the gap was done by Roberts and Demner - Fushman used a variety of natural language processing (NLP) techniques to know the difference between health questions asked by consumers and health professionals in different online question and answer (Q&A) platforms and have found that consumer questions tend to carry more misspelled medical terms, have longer background information, and resemble open-domain language more closely than texts written by professionals. One major factor of the gap is the contrast in medical vocabulary operated by consumers and health professionals.

SYNTHESIS

The above review of related literature suggests that the COVID-19 pandemic has made up to the point where it altered the perception of a lot of people in prioritizing their choices and preferences on how to live their lives and their careers in the so-called "new normal" in a life with a pandemic. Although the effects of the pandemic are mostly

negative, especially for the political aspects that it has brought up and highlighted more into, there is still some possibilities that happen as an effort to not leave everyone helpless during this situation of uncertainty. However, this does not bode well for our national development, as the current education of the Philippines is still rooting up for the foundations of K-12, which is structured towards producing students who are trained for jobs that are in demand locally and internationally, and as well as haltering the development of many innovations globally. Along with this, it has been inevitable that the learning that is under the distance learning strata is not that much as effective as it is to be in a normal set-up with teachers or professors meet up with their students.

This research paper then focused on the aspects of using numerous vocabularies since the implementation of the healthcare protocols to minimize the spread of the threat of the COVID-19 disease to the perspectives of high school students coming from Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School to understand what are their insights pertaining to this matter. While there are many radical groups and researchers that may be related or close to the topic that this paper is trying to present, there is a lack of study about the aspects of using numerous vocabularies on the students seen through their own lens, making the light to these studies as slightly impartial or lacking. And since further studies cannot be done that much due to the constraints brought by the pandemic as it was still threatening many vicinities in the Philippines, there is not much research done that could properly assess the issue of using a lot of jargon and assessing it regarding to its consequences. As a result, the researchers wanted to know the perspectives of the students themselves regarding such claims and whether the results would affirm them.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

Research Instrument

The research instrument used for the study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness*** is a survey questionnaire prepared by the researchers

using Google Forms. Google Forms is a free survey tool that is a part of the Google Suite, commonly known as Google Docs, which is Google's very own office suite that can collect information from people via personalized quizzes or surveys (Gavin, 2019).

The content of the survey is meant to determine the effect of using different jargon for the terminologies of health protocols mandated by the World Health Organization (WHO) and spearheaded in the Philippines by the Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) and the Department of Health (DOH) to their awareness of the happenings during the current pandemic. The utilization of surveys and questionnaires are the most common techniques in conducting quantitative research (Mersdorf, 2016).

Determining the Population Size

The chosen population for the study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness*** are the Junior High School (JHS) and Senior High School students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School (RMCHS) that is located in the heart of Cubao, an area inside the fourth district of Quezon City.

The researchers have decided that the said population is the best in studying to determine and evaluate the measures some of the terminologies that are officially given by the World Health Organization (WHO) before and during the lockdown and quarantine protocols that happened worldwide to spread the information campaign about the COVID-19 virus and the current pandemic.

For this study, the researchers would pick out 120 students, which is then divided into 20 people from various grade levels in the said population for obtaining the sample size. This is for the reason that (1) the population of the selected respondents is manageable enough to the current study and (2) for the ease of the sampling for the chosen respondents.

Determining the Sampling Technique

The sampling technique that will be used in this study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness*** is stratified sampling, a type of probability sampling. In probability sampling, everyone has an equal chance of being selected. This scheme is one in which every unit in the population has a chance (greater than zero) of being selected in the sample (Kenya Project Organization, 2012).

Stratified sampling is the most effective method when the study requires to get a representative sample of a population where it involves categorizing the members of the population into mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive groups. An independent simple random sample is then drawn from each group. Stratified sampling techniques provide more precise estimates if the population being surveyed is more heterogeneous than the categorized groups. This technique can enable the researcher to determine desired levels of sampling precision for each group, and can provide administrative efficiency. The main advantage of the approach is that it's able to give the most representative sample of a population (Hunt & Tyrrell, 2001; Kenya Project Organization, 2012).

Data Gathering Procedure

For the data gathering procedure of the study entitled, ***MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Various Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness***, it will be done by using survey questionnaires as the research instrument, which is hosted via Google Forms. This online survey that the researchers did is then separated by seven parts.

The first part is the introductory part for the online survey that was being done, along with a disclaimer about the privacy policy of the online survey hosting in accordance to the regulations of the Philippine law, specifically Republic Act (RA) 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012. By the provisions of the said law, only those that are directly tied or involved in the study will have access to the information that was being relayed using

Google Forms, the exchange of which will be facilitated through electronic mail (e-mail) messages or hard copy.

The second part is the collection of the demographic profiles of the respondents, which is meant to be sorted out after the survey hits the desired number of respondents. The required information from this section comprises of the following:

Demographic Profiling:

1. Name (Optional)

2. Gender

3. Grade Level

4. Strand (For Senior High School (SHS) Students)

The third part for the survey is the terminologies that are officially released by the World Health Organization (WHO) in their information campaign about the COVID-19 pandemic before and during the lockdown. The following terms that are utilized for this section of the survey is collected from some of the terminologies found in the glossary of terms about the pandemic that was continually published online by WebMD. These questions regarding the glossary of terms are as follows:

COVID-19 Terminologies Defined by WHO Before and During the Lockdown:

1. Are you familiar with the term, "Pandemic"?

2. Are you familiar with the term, "Coronavirus"?

3. Are you familiar with the term, "Respiratory Illness"?

- 4. Are you familiar with the term, "Droplet Transmission"?**
- 5. Are you familiar with the term, "Close Contact"?**
- 6. Are you familiar with the term, "Respiratory Symptoms"?**
- 7. Are you familiar with the term, "Mucosae"?**
- 8. Are you familiar with the term, "Conjunctiva"?**
- 9. Are you familiar with the term, "Airborne Transmission"?**
- 10. Are you familiar with the term, "Droplet Nuclei / Aerosols"?**
- 11. Are you familiar with the term, "Swabs"?**
- 12. Are you familiar with the term, "Hand Washing"?**
- 13. Are you familiar with the term, "Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)"?**

The fourth and fifth part of the survey for the study is similar to the third part; however, it focuses on the same assemblage of scenarios that will let the respondents to choose their responses constructed on their understandings on some of the terminologies that are given by the authorities of the Philippines before and during the lockdown to handle the dissemination of knowledge to the Filipino people, in the form of the Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) and the Department of Health (DOH). The given circumstances of the fourth and fifth part of the online survey is listed below:

COVID-19 Terminologies used in the Philippines Before the Lockdown:

- 1. Are you familiar with the term, "Carrier"?**
- 2. Are you familiar with the term, "Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)"?**
- 3. Are you familiar with the term, "Epidemic"?**
- 4. Are you familiar with the term, "Incubation Period"?**

5. *Are you familiar with the term, "Infect"?*
6. *Are you familiar with the term, "IATF - EID"?*
7. *Are you familiar with the term, "Local Transmission"?*
8. *Are you familiar with the term, "Mandatory"?*
9. *Are you familiar with the term, "Mandatory Quarantine"?*
10. *Are you familiar with the term, "Mild"?*
11. *Are you familiar with the term, "Mortality Rate"?*
12. *Are you familiar with the term, "Pandemic"?*
13. *Are you familiar with the term, "Patient Zero"?*
14. *Are you familiar with the term, "Physical Distancing"?*
15. *Are you familiar with the term, "Quarantine"?*
16. *Are you familiar with the term, "SARS - CoV - 2"?*
17. *Are you familiar with the term, "Self Quarantine"?*
18. *Are you familiar with the term, "Social Distancing"?*
19. *Are you familiar with the term, "Protocol"?*
20. *Are you familiar with the term, "Public Health Emergency (PHE)"?*
21. *Are you familiar with the term, "Triage"?*
22. *Are you familiar with the term, "Virus"?*

COVID-19 Terminologies used in the Philippines During the Lockdown:

1. *Are you familiar with the term, "Authorized Person Outside Residence (APOR)"?*

- 2. Are you familiar with the term, "Community Quarantine"?**
- 3. Are you familiar with the term, "Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ)"?**
- 4. Are you familiar with the term, "General Community Quarantine (ECQ)"?**
- 5. Are you familiar with the term, "High - Risk"?**
- 6. Are you familiar with the term, "Lockdown"?**
- 7. Are you familiar with the term, "Mass Testing"?**
- 8. Are you familiar with the term, "Modified"?**
- 9. Are you familiar with the term, "Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine (MECQ)"?**
- 10. Are you familiar with the term, "Modified General Community Quarantine (MECQ)"?**
- 11. Are you familiar with the term, "New Normal"?**
- 12. Are you familiar with the term, "Vaccine"?**

The sixth part is the part of verification of consent and authorization for the online survey that was being conducted by the researchers for the study, along with the reiteration on the privacy policy of the online survey hosting in accordance to the regulations of Republic Act (RA) 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012 whereas the survey respondent has the right to do the necessary activities in their information.

They are also well-informed with the validation of the information, by which it will be subsisting for a limited period, consistent with the purposes above or until otherwise revoked by another purpose regarding this matter. Survey respondents also has the right to ask for a copy of any personal information we hold about you, as well as to ask for it to be corrected, this has been made effective in accordance to the same law, the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

As this study is heavily reliant and is related to the situations that are present or have been present on the current pandemic that is caused by COVID-19, the researchers placed the seventh and final part of the survey to let their respondents to watch a list of videos found on YouTube regarding the matter if they have the luxury of time to watch the said videos. This has been done to educate them after the survey. Furthermore, as the researchers have found out that the survey may be too taxing for some students, this part of the survey also has links for the redirection of music videos from popular Korean pop groups for the sake of their entertainment.

Encapsulating the known fact that this type of online survey accumulates sensitive data, as well as with the compliance of the law, the following information gathered will only be used as crucial information for the undergoing research study.

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MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Different Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness

Greetings!

(Pagbati!)

The senior high school students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School would be conducting a survey for their research entitled, "MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Different Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness" as a requirement to the subject, Inquiries, Investigations, and Immersion (3I).

(Ang mga mag-aaral ng senior high school ng Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School ay magsasagawa ng isang survey para sa kanilang pagsasaliksik na pinamagatang, "MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Different Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness" bilang isang kinakailangan sa aming paksa, ang Inquiries, Investigations, and Immersion (3I).)

This survey form is intended for the students of Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School in evaluating the usage of different semantic terms of the different terminologies for the health protocols to their awareness of the happenings during the current pandemic.

(Ang form ng survey na ito ay inilaan para sa mga mag-aaral ng Ramon Magsaysay (Cubao) High School sa pagsusuri ng paggamit ng iba't ibang mga terminong semantiko ng iba't ibang mga terminolohiya para sa mga protocol sa kalusugan sa kanilang kamalayan sa mga nangyari sa kasalukuyang pandemiya.)

Survey Disclaimer:

The collected personal information will be utilized solely by the proponents for documentation, statistical reports, and processing purposes within the study entitled, "MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Different Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness" and will not be shared with any outside parties except to specified people who will request a copy of the statistical information (i.e. Research Adviser and the Teaching Department and Faculty) due to the provisions of Republic Act 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Only those involved in the study will have access to this personal information, the exchange of which will be facilitated through email or hard copy. The data will be kept in a clean format

under the secured storage of Google Forms, Google Slides, and the local computer drives of the authorized personnel.

(Ang mga kasangkot lamang sa pag-aaral ang magkakaroon ng access sa personal na impormasyong ito, na ang pagpapalitan nito ay mapapadali sa pamamagitan ng email o hard copy. Ang data ay malinis na itatago sa ilalim ng ligtas na pag-iimbak ng Google Forms, Google Slides, at mga lokal na computer drive ng mga awtorisadong tauhan.)

The compiled data will be used as reference information for the undergoing research study. You have the right to edit your submission in this survey as long as it will not tamper with our data during the time period of this study.

(Ang naipong data ay gagamitin bilang sanggunian na impormasyon para sa sumasailalim na pag-aaral ng pananaliksik. Mayroon kang karapatang i-edit ang iyong pagsusumite sa survey na ito hangga't hindi ito makagambala sa aming data sa tagal ng panahon ng pag-aaral na ito.)

You have also the right to ask for a copy of any personal information we hold about you, as well as to ask for it to be corrected. To do so, you may contact the following people:

(Mayroon ka ring karapatang humiling ng isang kopya ng anumang personal na impormasyon na hawak namin tungkol sa iyo, pati na rin humiling na maitama ito. Upang magawa ito, maaari kang makipag-ugnay sa mga sumusunod:)

Ms. Generosa E. Ibasco - Teacher (Guro), Inquiries, Investigations, and Immersion (3I)
E-mail: generosa.ibasco@depedqc.ph

Mr. Mark Jonel V. Abad - Proponent
E-mail: markjonel.abad@gmail.com

Mr. John Vincent A. Aniano - Proponent
E-mail: thisisjohnvincent@gmail.com

Ms. Jemalyn J. Avila - Proponent
E-mail: jemalynavila@gmail.com

Mr. Andrei Nathaniel D. Batugal - Proponent
E-mail: dukerodriguez66613@gmail.com

Mr. Marc Andrie M. Bermundo - Proponent
E-mail: marcandrie.bermundo@gmail.com

Ms. Ira Mae M. Campollo - Proponent
E-mail: campollo.ira.mae.stem@gmail.com

Ms. Marjorie J. Cortiguerra - Proponent
E-mail: mcortiguerra27@gmail.com

Ms. Mary Joy R. Jalandoni - Proponent

E-mail: majoyjalandoni@gmail.com

* Required

1. By clicking or tapping "I agree", you are accepting to answer all of the questions that are present in this survey. (Sa pamamagitan ng pag-click o pag-tap sa "Sumasang-ayon ako", tumatanggap ka upang sagutin ang lahat ng mga katanungan na naroroon sa survey na ito.) *

Mark only one oval.

I agree. (Sumasang-ayon ako.)

Demographic
Profiling
(Pagtatala ng
mga
Demograpiko)

This part of the survey is to assess the demographic status of the survey respondent which will then be sorted out after the survey has the desired number of respondents.

(Ang bahaging ito ng pagsusuri ay upang masuri ang katayuan ng demograpiko ng sumasagot sa nasabing pagsusuri (ikaw) upang ang mga resulta ay maaayos pagkatapos na maabot ng survey ang nais na bilang ng mga respondente.)

A truthful response is required for this survey, so feel free to take some time in answering these questions.

(Ang isang makatotohanang tugon ay kinakailangan para sa survey na ito, kaya huwag mag-atubiling maglaan ng kaunting oras sa pagsagot sa mga katanungang ito.)

2. Name / Pangalan (Optional) *

3. Gender / Kasarian *

Mark only one oval.

Female

Male

Prefer not to say

4. Grade Level / Antas ng Baitang *

Mark only one oval.

- Grade 7
- Grade 8
- Grade 9
- Grade 10
- Grade 11
- Grade 12

5. Strand (For SHS Students only. / Para sa mga estudyante ng SHS lamang.)

Mark only one oval.

- Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM)
- Accountancy and Business Management (ABM)
- General Academic Strand (GAS)
- Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS)

COVID-19 Terminologies
Defined by WHO Before
and During the Lockdown
(Mga Terminolohiya na
Tinukoy ng WHO ukol sa
COVID-19 Bago at
Habang Nagaganap ang
Lockdown)

This part of the survey is to assess the knowledge that is known by the student on some of the terminologies that are officially given by the World Health Organization (WHO) before and during the lockdown and quarantine protocols that happened worldwide to spread the information campaign about the COVID-19 virus and the current pandemic.

(Ang bahaging ito ng pagsusuri ay ginawa upang makita ang kaalaman na nalalaman ng mag-aaral sa mga iilang terminolohiya na opisyal na ibinigay ng World Health Organization (WHO) bago at habang nangyayari ang mga lockdown at mga kuwarantenang protocols sa buong mundo upang kumalat ang kampanya sa impormasyon tungkol sa COVID-19 virus at sa kasalukuyang pandemya.)

A truthful response is required for this survey, so feel free to take some time in answering these questions.

(Ang isang makatotohanang tugon ay kinakailangan para sa survey na ito, kaya huwag mag-atubiling maglaan ng kaunting oras sa pagsagot sa mga katanungang ito.)

To know more about the terminologies that are officially given by the World Health Organization (WHO) to spread the information campaign about the COVID-19 virus and the current pandemic, refer to the link below:

(Upang malaman ang higit pa tungkol sa mga terminolohiya na opisyal na ibinigay ng World Health Organization (WHO) upang kumalat ang kampanya sa impormasyon tungkol sa COVID-19 virus at ang kasalukuyang pandemya, sumangguni sa link sa ibaba:)

Coronavirus: Glossary of Common Terms:

<https://www.webmd.com/lung/coronavirus-glossary#1>

6. Are you familiar with the term, "Pandemic"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Pandemic"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

7. Are you familiar with the term, "Coronavirus"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Coronavirus"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

8. Are you familiar with the term, "Respiratory Illness"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Respiratory Illness"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

9. Are you familiar with the term, "Droplet Transmission"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Droplet Transmission"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

10. Are you familiar with the term, "Close Contact"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Close Contact"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

11. Are you familiar with the term, "Respiratory Symptoms"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Respiratory Symptoms"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

12. Are you familiar with the term, "Mucosae"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Mucosae"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

13. Are you familiar with the term, "Conjunctiva"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Conjunctiva"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

14. Are you familiar with the term, "Airborne Transmission"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Airborne Transmission"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

15. Are you familiar with the term, "Droplet Nuclei / Aerosols"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Droplet Nuclei / Aerosols"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

16. Are you familiar with the term, "Swabs"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Swabs"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

17. Are you familiar with the term, "Hand Washing"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Hand Washing"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

18. Are you familiar with the term, "Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

COVID-19
Terminologies used in
the Philippines Before
the Lockdown (Mga
Terminolohiya na
ginagamit sa Pilipinas
ukol sa COVID-19
Bago ang Lockdown)

This part of the survey is to assess the knowledge that is known by the student on some of the terminologies that are given by the authorities of the Philippines before the lockdown to handle the dissemination of knowledge to the Filipino people, in the form of the Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) and the Department of Health (DOH).

(Ang bahaging ito ng pagsusuri ay upang matukoy ang kaalamang nalalaman ng mag-aaral sa mga iilang terminolohiya na ibinibigay ng mga awtoridad ng Pilipinas bago ang naturang lockdown upang hawakan ang pagpapalaganap ng kaalaman sa sambayanang Pilipino, sa pamamagitan ng Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) at ng Department of Health (DOH).)

A truthful response is required for this survey, so feel free to take some time in answering these questions.

(Ang isang makatotohanang tugon ay kinakailangan para sa survey na ito, kaya huwag mag-atubiling maglaan ng kaunting oras sa pagsagot sa mga katanungang ito.)

To know more about the terminologies that are given by the authorities of the Philippines to handle the dissemination of knowledge to the Filipino people, refer to the link below:

(Upang malaman ang higit pa tungkol sa mga terminolohiya na ibinibigay ng mga awtoridad ng Pilipinas para mahawakan ang pagpapalaganap ng kaalaman sa sambayanang Pilipino, sumangguni sa link sa ibaba:)

Google Philippines - Isang Gabay sa mga Salitang Kaugnay ng COVID-19:
<https://www.diksiyonaryongcovid19.com/>

19. Are you familiar with the term, "Carrier"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Carrier"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

20. Are you familiar with the term, "Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19)"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

21. Are you familiar with the term, "Epidemic"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Epidemic"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

22. Are you familiar with the term, "Incubation Period"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Incubation Period"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

23. Are you familiar with the term, "Infect"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Infect"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

24. Are you familiar with the term, "IATF - EID"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "IATF - EID"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

25. Are you familiar with the term, "Local Transmission"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Local Transmission"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

26. Are you familiar with the term, "Mandatory"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Mandatory"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

27. Are you familiar with the term, "Mandatory Quarantine"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Mandatory Quarantine"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

28. Are you familiar with the term, "Mild"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Mild"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

29. Are you familiar with the term, "Mortality Rate"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Mortality Rate"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

30. Are you familiar with the term, "Pandemic"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Pandemic"?)*

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

31. Are you familiar with the term, "Patient Zero"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Patient Zero"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

32. Are you familiar with the term, "Physical Distancing"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Physical Distancing"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

33. Are you familiar with the term, "Quarantine"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Quarantine"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

34. Are you familiar with the term, "SARS - CoV - 2"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "SARS - CoV - 2") *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

35. Are you familiar with the term, "Self Quarantine"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Self Quarantine") *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

36. Are you familiar with the term, "Social Distancing"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Social Distancing") *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

37. Are you familiar with the term, "Protocol"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Protocol"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

38. Are you familiar with the term, "Public Health Emergency (PHE)"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Public Health Emergency (PHE)"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

39. Are you familiar with the term, "Triage"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Triage"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

40. Are you familiar with the term, "Virus"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Virus"?) *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
 No (Hindi)
 Maybe (Maaari)

COVID-19
Terminologies used in
the Philippines During
the Lockdown (Mga
Terminolohiya na
ginagamit sa Pilipinas
ukol sa COVID-19
Habang Nagaganap
ang Lockdown)

This part of the survey is to assess the knowledge that is known by the student on some of the terminologies that are given by the authorities of the Philippines during the lockdown to handle the dissemination of knowledge to the Filipino people, in the form of the Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) and the Department of Health (DOH).

(Ang bahaging ito ng pagsusuri ay upang matukoy ang kaalamang nalalaman ng mag-aaral sa mga iilang terminolohiya na ibinibigay ng mga awtoridad ng Pilipinas habang nagaganap ang naturang lockdown upang hawakan ang pagpapalaganap ng kaalaman sa sambayanang Pilipino, sa pamamagitan ng Inter-Agency Task Force on Emerging Infectious Diseases (IATF-EID) at ng Department of Health (DOH).)

A truthful response is required for this survey, so feel free to take some time in answering these questions.

(Ang isang makatotohanang tugon ay kinakailangan para sa survey na ito, kaya huwag mag-atubiling maglaan ng kaunting oras sa pagsagot sa mga katanungang ito.)

To know more about the terminologies that are given by the authorities of the Philippines to handle the dissemination of knowledge to the Filipino people, refer to the link below:

(Upang malaman ang higit pa tungkol sa mga terminolohiya na ibinibigay ng mga awtoridad ng Pilipinas para mahawakan ang pagpapalaganap ng kaalaman sa sambayanang Pilipino, sumangguni sa link sa ibaba:)

Google Philippines - Isang Gabay sa mga Salitang Kaugnay ng COVID-19: <https://www.diksyonaryongcovid19.com/>

41. Are you familiar with the term, "Authorized Person Outside Residence (APOR)"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Authorized Person Outside Residence (APOR)"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

42. Are you familiar with the term, "Community Quarantine"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Community Quarantine"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

43. Are you familiar with the term, "Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ)"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Enhanced Community Quarantine (ECQ)"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

44. Are you familiar with the term, "General Community Quarantine (GCQ)"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "General Community Quarantine (GCQ)"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

45. Are you familiar with the term, "High - Risk"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "High - Risk"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

46. Are you familiar with the term, "Lockdown"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Lockdown"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

47. Are you familiar with the term, "Mass Testing"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Mass Testing"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

48. Are you familiar with the term, "Modified"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Modified"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

49. Are you familiar with the term, "Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine (MECQ)"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Modified Enhanced Community Quarantine (MECQ)"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

50. Are you familiar with the term, "Modified General Community Quarantine (MGCQ)"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Modified General Community Quarantine (MGCQ)"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

51. Are you familiar with the term, "New Normal"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "New Normal"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

52. Are you familiar with the term, "Vaccine"? (Pamilyar ka ba sa terminong "Vaccine"?)

Mark only one oval.

- Yes (Oo)
- No (Hindi)
- Maybe (Maaari)

Verification of
Consent and
Authorization (Pag-
verify ng Pahintulot at
Pagpatnugot)

This section of this survey is for verifying your consent on the responses that you have submitted for this survey.

(Ang seksyong ito sa pagsusuring ibinigay ay para sa pagpapatunay ng iyong pahintulot sa mga tugon na isinumite ng siyang sumagot.)

Reiterating the introduction of the survey earlier, the survey respondent were made aware of the rights under the Data Privacy Act, including the following:

(Naulit ang pagpapakilala ng survey nang mas maaga, ang respondent sa survey ay napagtanto ang mga karapatan sa ilalim ng Batas sa Pagkakatago ng Datos ng 2012, kasama ang mga sumusunod:)

1. The right to access my personal information; (Ang karapatang mag-access ng aking personal na impormasyon.)
2. The right to make corrections to my personal information; (Ang karapatang gumawa ng mga pagwawasto sa aking personal na impormasyon.)
3. The right to object to the processing of my personal information; (Ang karapatang sumalungat sa pagpoproseso ng aking personal na impormasyon.)
4. The right to erasure or blocking of my personal information; (Ang karapatang burahin o hadlangan ang aking personal na impormasyon.)
5. The right to be informed of the existence of processing my personal information; (Karapatang maipaalam sa pagkakaroon ng pagproseso ng aking personal na impormasyon.)
6. The right to damages; (Ang karapatang makapinsala.)
7. The right to lodge a complaint before the National Privacy Commission. (Ang karapatang magsumite ng reklamo sa harap ng National Privacy Commission.)

This consent and authorization remains valid and subsisting for a limited period consistent with the purposes above or until otherwise revoked by another purpose regarding this matter.

(Ang pahintulot at pagpatnugot na ito ay mananatiling wasto at nabubuhay para sa isang limitadong panahon na naaayon sa mga layunin sa itaas o hanggang sa kung hindi man bawiin ng ibang layunin tungkol sa bagay na ito.)

The respondent also has the right to ask for a copy of any personal information we hold about you, as well as to ask for it to be corrected. To do so, you may contact the following people:

(Mayroon ka ring karapatang humiling ng isang kopya ng anumang personal na impormasyon na hawak namin tungkol sa iyo, pati na rin humiling na maitama ito. Upang magawa ito, maaari kang makipag-ugnay sa mga sumusunod:)

Ms. Generosa E. Ibasco - Teacher (Guro), Inquiries, Investigations, and Immersion (3I)
E-mail: generosa.ibasco@depedqc.ph

Mr. Mark Jonel V. Abad - Proponent
E-mail: markjonel.abad@gmail.com

Mr. John Vincent A. Aniano - Proponent
E-mail: thisisjohnvincent@gmail.com

Ms. Jemalyn J. Avila - Proponent
E-mail: jemalynavila@gmail.com

Mr. Andrei Nathaniel D. Batugal - Proponent
E-mail: dukerodriguez66613@gmail.com

Mr. Marc Andrie M. Bermundo - Proponent
E-mail: marcandrie.bermundo@gmail.com

Ms. Ira Mae M. Campollo - Proponent
E-mail: campollo.ira.mae.stem@gmail.com

Ms. Marjorie J. Cortiguerra - Proponent
E-mail: mcortiguerra27@gmail.com

Ms. Mary Joy R. Jalandoni - Proponent
E-mail: majoyjalandoni@gmail.com

53. By clicking or tapping "I agree", the answers that you have given to these questions that are present in this survey are truthful and shall be only be processed in a legal manner. (Sa pamamagitan ng pag-click o pag-tap sa "Sumasang-ayon ako", ang mga sagot na iyong ibinigay sa mga katanungang ito na naroroon sa survey na ito ay totoo at at mapoproseso lamang sa isang ligal na pamamaraan.) *

Mark only one oval.

I agree. (Sumasang-ayon ako.)

MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Different Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness | Response: Submitted (MonSAY: Evaluating the Impact of Using Different Semantic Terms in Describing Health Protocols to Students' Pandemic Awareness | Tugon: Isinumite)

Thank you for taking your time to respond to this online survey, dear respondent!

(Salamat sa paglalaan ng iyong oras upang tumugon sa online survey na ito, mahal na tumutugon!)

As this study is relating on the current pandemic that is caused by COVID-19, the researchers would also like you, the respondent of this survey, to watch the following videos if you have the luxury of time to watch the said videos. The video titles and links are shown below:

(Tulad ng pag-aaral na ito ay nauugnay sa kasalukuyang pandemya na sanhi ng COVID-19, nais rin ng mga mananaliksik, ang tumutugon sa pagsusuri na ito, na panoorin ang mga sumusunod na video kung mayroon kang luho ng oras upang mapanood ang mga nasabing video. Ang mga pamagat ng video at mga link ay ipinapakita sa ibaba:)

1. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i0ZabxXmH4Y>
2. What is COVID-19? - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7z0kzYpughw>
3. Recognizing Day to Day Signs and Symptoms of Coronavirus - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7z0kzYpughw>
4. How the Covid-19 pandemic began - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0RKCTCweY4I>
5. DOH: COVID-19 vaccine turnout still high despite order vs brand announcements | ABS-CBN News - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FOSjwxnNIVM>
6. BIDA Solusyon sa COVID 19! - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5ruNClwyBOK>
7. COVID-19: Know The Symptoms - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mf26ydgMY24>
8. How to stay safe from COVID-19 - Tagalog - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MaKf1JsSjSg>
9. COVID19 Vaccines - Vaccine Development Times - Filipino - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_YEwx9oKqos
10. COVID-19 Vaccines - Tagalog - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bK8UbqRaoSY>

Again, thank you for answering this survey!

(Muli, nagpapasalamat kami sa iyong pagsagot sa aming pagsusuri!)

While this seems to be a perplexing and complicated survey, the researchers would also like to plug these videos in to stream for your enjoyment.

(Habang ito ay tila isang nakakagulo at kumplikadong survey, nais din ng mga

mananaliksik na i-plug ang mga video na ito upang mag-stream para sa iyong kasiyahan.)

1. BTS (방탄소년단) 'Butter' Official MV - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WMweEpGlu_U
2. [MV] 이달의 소녀 (LOONA) "Star"- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zW-AIXAnLcE>
3. [MV] Weeekly(위클리) _ After School - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qfVuRQX0ydQ>
4. [MV] 이달의 소녀/췌 (LOONA/Chuu) "Heart Attack" - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BVVfMFS3mgc>
5. [MV] 이달의 소녀 (LOONA) "Why Not?" - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b6li05zh3Kg>
6. ENHYPEN (엔하이픈) 'Drunk-Dazed' Official MV - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Fc7-Oe0tj5k>
6. STAYC(스테이씨) 'ASAP' MV - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NsY-9MCOIAQ>
7. ITZY "마.피.아. In the morning" M/V - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_ysomCGaZLw
8. TWICE [Kura Kura] Music Video - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BSS8Y-0hOiy>
9. TWICE [BETTER] Music Video - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sLmLwgxnPUE>
10. [MV] 이달의 소녀/하슬 (LOONA/HaSeul) "소년, 소녀 (Let Me In)" - <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6a4BWpBJjpl>

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